

A decentralised hydrogen-based trigeneration system with multi-energy storage for grid-independent operation

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Abstract

Energy storage plays a crucial role in addressing renewable energy variability by enabling controllable power flow and improving system flexibility. This study develops a novel standalone hydrogen-based trigeneration system incorporating renewable energy resources, heat pumps, and hybrid energy storage systems (HESS), including hydrogen storage systems (HSS), battery energy storage systems (BESS) and thermal energy storage (TES). A linear programming framework is applied to simultaneously optimise both system design and operation while minimising total annualised cost. The results indicate that BESS primarily supports short-term balancing, while HSS functions as a long-term energy carrier, and TES maintains heat supply under resource uncertainty. Adopting HSS results in 11% of BESS and 6% of TES reduction compared to a stand-alone battery system. Moreover, sensitivity analysis shows that reducing hydrogen cost will substantially increase the installed hydrogen infrastructure. At 90% cost reduction, hydrogen storage and fuel cell capacity increases fourfold to 8.38 MWh and 0.44 MW, respectively, and electrolyser capacity inclines at 0.79 MW of the baseline model. The reduction of hydrogen investment cost can potentially accelerate hydrogen penetration and enhance overall performance.

Keywords

energy storage system, hydrogen, flexibility, decentralised trigeneration system

1 Introduction

As the world faces the urgent need to phase out fossil fuels, renewable energy has been increasingly explored as a sustainable alternative. However, its inherent intermittency creates supply-demand imbalances, posing challenges to energy system reliability. Decentralised energy systems that integrate multi-vector technologies have emerged as a promising approach to enhance system resilience while promoting low-carbon solutions. Combining with energy storage is particularly appealing due to its ability to store surplus energy and bridge the temporal mismatch between generation and demand, facilitating more efficient energy distribution to households. Furthermore, the need to oversize renewable generation capacity can be mitigated by incorporating energy storage systems, thereby reducing the overall capital cost [1]. Battery energy storage systems (BESS) store surplus electricity generated from renewable sources during high production

periods and discharge it when renewables are insufficient or during peak demand. Unfortunately, BESS is primarily suited for short-term energy storage due to its limited energy density. Conversely, hydrogen storage systems (HSS) enable long-term energy storage by converting excess power into hydrogen through an electrolyser, which can be stored in a hydrogen tank and later reconverted to electricity using a fuel cell (FC) during periods of low renewables availability, increased demand, or unexpected events, such as extreme weather, blackouts, and failures [2]. In addition, FC produces recoverable heat to meet heating and cooling demands, particularly during thermal deficit. This enhances overall system efficiency, lowers capital and operational costs, and reduces carbon emissions [3]. A study reported that incorporating HSS with BESS can reduce operating costs by up to 35% and carbon emissions by 33% compared to using BESS alone [2].

Furthermore, thermal energy storage (TES) provides an effective solution for storing and releasing heat energy when thermal demand exceeds supply. The integration of TES improves the efficiency and flexibility of the thermal subsystem [4]. Kohole et al. [1] investigated that the combination of solar photovoltaic, wind turbine, and TES is the most effective and cost-efficient configuration for meeting small, medium, and heavy activities. Xu et al. [5] presented a residential energy system combining a solid oxide fuel cell-based combined cooling, heating, and power (SOFC-CCHP) unit, battery, and hot water tank. The integration enhances the overall system and exergy efficiencies of a residence while reducing daily cost and annual emissions.

Hybrid energy storage systems (HESS), which combine multiple storage units, have gained increasing attention by leveraging the complementary strengths of different storage types, leading to enhanced system reliability and economic performance [6]. Nevertheless, there are still limited studies that integrate three layers of energy storage to fulfil electricity, heating, and cooling for grid-independent operation. Therefore, this study proposes a novel integrated design and optimisation of a fully decentralised hydrogen-based trigeneration system that simultaneously combines three-layer energy storage (BESS, HSS, and TES) with a heat pump (HP) for grid-independent operation. Unlike existing studies that typically focus on dual-storage configurations, this work captures the complementary roles of short-, medium-, and long-term energy storage within a unified optimisation framework. In the present study, the system is analysed under autonomous operation with hourly resolution, enabling a detailed assessment of seasonal and intra-day variability across electricity, heating, and cooling demands. Moreover, a sensitivity analysis on hydrogen investment cost is conducted to investigate its influence on system configuration and technology deployment.

2 Methodology

Household energy demand data were obtained from open-source datasets representing a residential area in Switzerland for the year 2015 [7]. The dataset comprises three hourly load

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profiles (electricity, heating, and cooling demands). The dataset adopted in this study offers high-resolution data that effectively represents the temporal variability of household energy consumption. It is important to emphasise that this work does not seek to replicate a specific existing condition of Swiss grid-connected or grid-independent systems. Instead, it proposes a generalised system design under representative conditions to enhance the broader applicability and interpretability of results. Corresponding historical weather data, including solar irradiance, temperature, and wind speed, were sourced from Open-Meteo for the year 2015.

To evaluate the performance of the proposed decentralised hydrogen-enabled energy system, a linear programming (LP) framework was adopted due to its simplicity and computational efficiency. As a result, it has the ability to handle large-scale optimisation problems with numerous variables and constraints. This approach has been widely applied in the optimisation of energy systems at the domestic level [8]. The model was implemented using PyPSA, an open-source Python-based framework for energy system optimisation.

The proposed system integrates hydrogen technologies, including an electrolyser, a fuel cell micro-CCHP, and hydrogen storage, alongside HP, battery, and TES (see Fig. 1). The heat pump acts as a reversible unit, which can supply both heating and cooling. Renewable energy sources—solar photovoltaics (PV) and wind turbines (WT)—are used as the primary energy inputs for hydrogen production and load supply.

Figure 1: A decentralised hydrogen-based energy system with multi-energy storage and HP

The optimisation framework determined the optimal capacities and operation of all system components under fully unconstrained conditions, forming a baseline configuration. The study compared the performance of the baseline model with that of a conventional battery-only system. Subsequently, a sensitivity analysis on hydrogen capital expenditure (CAPEX) was conducted to assess its influence on system design and hydrogen utilisation. The hydrogen CAPEX was progressively reduced in 10% increments relative to its initial value. The key parameters used in this study are summarised in Table 1.

In this study, the objective function of the decentralised hydrogen-enabled energy systems is to minimise the total system cost. Annualised cost is defined as the annual cost of the system over its lifetime, calculated by annualising the capital investment using the capital recovery factor (CRF) and summing it with the annual operation and maintenance (O&M) costs. CRF is calculated using Eq. (1) [14].

$$\text{CRF}(i, N) = \frac{i(1+i)^N}{(1+i)^N - 1} \quad (1)$$

Table 1: Key Parameters

Components	Parameters	Values	Refs
Solar PV	Efficiency	20%	[9]
	Capital cost	\$1100/kW	[10]
	Lifetime	20 years	[11]
Wind turbine	Capital cost	\$2500/kW	[10]
	Lifetime	30 years	[11]
Battery	Efficiency	95%	[12]
	Self-discharge rate	0.02%	[13]
	Capital cost	\$550/kWh	[10]
	Lifetime	15 years	[11]
Inverter	Efficiency	95%	[14]
	Capital cost	\$200/kW	[10]
	Lifetime	15 years	[11]
Electrolyser	Efficiency	70%	[15]
	Capital cost	\$1500/kW	[16]
	Lifetime	15 years	[11]
Fuel cell	Electrical efficiency	50%	[14]
	Heat efficiency	46%	[17]
	Capital cost	\$2400/kW	[18]
	Lifetime	20 years	[9]
Hydrogen storage	Efficiency	95%	[14]
	Capital cost	\$2100/kg	[19]
	Lifetime	20 years	[11]
TES	Efficiency	90%	[20]
	Self-discharge rate	0.063%	[20]
	Capital cost	\$543/kWh	[21]
	Lifetime	20 years	[1]
Heat pump	COP heating	3	[22]
	COP cooling	3	[22]
	Capital cost	\$1624/kW	[23]
	Lifetime	20 years	[23]
All components	OM cost	3% of capital cost	[24]

Where i denotes the annual interest rate, assumed to be 5%, and N represents the lifetime of each component. The annualised cost of each component is determined using Eq. (2), with j indicating the corresponding system component [14].

$$\text{Total annualised cost} = \sum_j \left(\text{Capital cost}_j \times \text{CRF} \right) + \text{OM cost}_j \quad (2)$$

3 Results and Discussion

As depicted in Fig. 2, solar irradiance peaked between June and August, exceeding 800 W/m^2 . Thereafter, the intensity gradually declined, falling to approximately half of its peak value by December. By contrast, wind speeds were the highest during the winter months, from December to March, with a peak above 12 m/s in December. Lower wind speeds were observed during the summer period, particularly from June to September.

Fig. 3 shows the trend of residential electricity demand. During winter, electricity demand reached its peak at approximately 700 kW , decreased by around 200 kW during warmer months, and then increased again to a comparable level toward the end of the

Figure 2: Weather trend in 2015: (a) Solar irradiance and (b) Wind speed

Figure 3: Weekly residential electricity demand during a) winter and b) summer

Figure 4: Annual residential a) heating and b) cooling demand

year. Both winter and summer showed the same pattern, with the load remaining very low at night, dropping below 100 kW. The demand then increased sharply during the morning peak (around 6:00 am), remained high during midday, and hit another peak in the evening (around 5:00-6:00 pm). Thereafter, the electricity load gradually declined from approximately 10:00 pm and returned to low levels until the following morning.

As illustrated in Fig. 4, colder months exhibited the highest overall energy demand, exceeding 2000 kW, driven by space heating and hot water requirements. Heating demand persisted during summer to satisfy domestic hot water, though its magnitude was only about one-tenth of that in the winter. Conversely, cooling demand was concentrated during the summer. The cooling demand emerged from around April to October and increased substantially during the summer months. The demand was massively needed between June and August, touching a point of approximately 1750 kW in August. In April, the need for cooling remained relatively low at around 200 kW, while the demand in October was lower than in April.

3.1 Baseline model

Optimisation results indicate that solar PV power output was more dominant than WT owing to its relatively stable availability throughout the year, rising its attractiveness in an off-grid configuration. As a result, the optimal installed capacity of solar PV (21.43 MW) was significantly higher than that of the WT (0.52 MW). The relatively small WT capacity reflects the site-specific wind resource conditions and cost assumptions adopted within the optimisation framework, resulting in only minimally viable installation.

Due to its high round-trip efficiency and cost-effectiveness, BESS plays a primary role in meeting household electricity demand, resulting in a comparatively large installed storage capacity of 23.31 MWh. By comparison, HSS was deployed at smaller capacities, with hydrogen storage, electrolyser, and FC micro-CCHP capacities of 2.14 MWh, 0.18 MW, and 0.10 MW, respectively. The distinction capacity between electrolyser and FC micro-CCHP indicates that the electrolyser is sized to maximise hydrogen production and minimise renewable energy curtailment, while FC micro-CCHP capacity operates as a demand-following unit, designed to cover peak and deficit periods.

(a) Winter

(b) Summer

Figure 5: Electricity supply and demand for two weeks: (a) Winter and (b) Summer

(a) Winter

(b) Summer

Figure 6: Heating supply and demand for two weeks: (a) Winter and (b) Summer

(a) Winter

(b) Summer

Figure 7: Cooling supply and demand for two weeks: (a) Winter and (b) Summer

Figure 8: Baseline vs Battery-only

For the thermal subsystem, the optimal capacities of HP and TES were 0.61 MW and 3.68 MWh, respectively, indicating their importance in meeting heating and cooling demand and managing thermal energy balance. The total annualised system cost was estimated at \$4,757,354, demonstrating the trade-offs among renewable generation, storage technologies, and system reliability under non-grid-connected conditions.

Fig. 5 illustrates that the residential electricity demand is primarily supplied by solar PV and the battery. In winter, dispatched PV power was two times higher than that in summer owing to reduced curtailment, whereas a larger fraction of PV generation during warmer months was curtailed due to surplus supply. Similarly, the WT contribution was about twice in winter than in summer, which compensates for reduced solar radiation intensity.

Figure 9: Sensitivity analysis

However, WT contribution was lower than that of PV. During the periods of lower solar irradiance, the battery was charged and discharged more frequently, about twofold, to provide short-term balancing and smooth temporal mismatches in supply-demand.

In contrast, HSS remains largely inactive during summer conditions, when renewable generation is sufficient to directly satisfy demand, and any surplus is prioritised for short-term storage. In winter, however, excess renewable electricity is increasingly directed to operate the electrolyser for hydrogen production. The stored hydrogen was subsequently converted via FC micro-CCHP to generate electricity, thereby meeting demand when both renewables and the battery are insufficient. This underscores the role of HSS as a long-term energy buffer to address supply deficits during peak seasons and limited renewable generation.

HP exhibits higher electricity consumption in order to meet increased heating demand during colder months than in summer. This is consistent with the seasonal heating and cooling load profiles. Additionally, any excess electricity that could not be economically stored was discharged via a dump load to avoid oversizing system components, demonstrating the optimisation trade-off between storage expansion and curtailment costs within the system design.

As can be seen in Fig. 6, HP plays a pivotal role in satisfying thermal energy demand across both winter and summer periods. Due to significantly higher heating requirements, HP operating load increased by approximately sixfold compared to summer conditions. TES complements HP operation by mitigating temporal mismatches between heat generation and demand, storing excess thermal energy during winter, and supplying heat deficits when required. In contrast, TES was not operated during summer, indicating its dominant role in seasonal heat balancing. FC micro-CCHP further supports thermal reliability when both HP and TES were unable to fully meet heating demand, reflecting the role of hydrogen as a flexible energy carrier.

Meanwhile, cooling demand was observed only during the summer period and was fully met by HP. (see Fig. 7). No cooling demand arose during winter, further emphasising the seasonal nature of cooling needs and the distinct operational roles of system components across different periods.

3.2 Comparison of system configurations

This subsection presents a comparative analysis between the baseline system and a battery-only configuration to evaluate differences in optimal capacity allocation and total system cost. The baseline model integrated a hybrid energy storage system,

comprising BESS, TES, and HSS, whereas, the comparison case relies on BESS and TES.

As depicted in Fig. 8, the capacity of PV went down slightly to 21.02 MW, while the WT capacity fell by over 50% to 0.19 MW, indicating a lower WT contribution supply. The battery capacity in the standalone configuration increased from 23.31 MWh to 26.18 MWh. Likewise, a slight upward in TES capacity from 3.68 MWh to 3.93 MWh was shown to satisfy heating demand. Consequently, the total annualised cost rose marginally to \$4,769,895, indicating that the baseline model was more cost-effective. Notably, the heat pump capacity remained unchanged, suggesting that the primary differences arise from generation and storage system design rather than conversion technologies.

These results indicate that in the absence of HSS, the system becomes more dependent on short-term technologies to manage both intra-day variability and longer-duration energy deficits. As a result, both BESS and TES capacities must be increased to maintain system reliability. Conversely, the adoption of HSS introduces a long-term storage pathway that can absorb excess renewable generation and supply energy during prolonged periods of low resource availability. This led to a reduction in the capacities of both BESS and TES by around 11% and 6%, respectively. The hybrid configuration enables a more balanced and efficient allocation of storage roles across different technologies, leading to contributing to improved cost performance.

3.3 Sensitivity Analysis

A sensitivity analysis of hydrogen CAPEX is performed to evaluate the impact of reduced hydrogen upfront costs on system design and hydrogen utilisation. The hydrogen capital cost was reduced in steps of 10% from its baseline value. As shown in Fig. 9, the results demonstrated a gradual decrease in total annualised system cost, with a reduction of merely 2.2%, from \$4,757,354 to \$4,653,517, when hydrogen CAPEX was cut down by 90%. The cost reduction, however, drives a strong upward shift in terms of hydrogen technology configurations.

Hydrogen storage capacity increased significantly, rising four-fold from 2.14 MWh to 8.38 MWh. Similarly, FC capacity jumped between 0.10 MW and 0.44 MW. Also, a substantial increase in electrolyser capacity was observed, from 0.18 MW to 0.79 MW. The capacity of the electrolyser may exceed that of the FC, since hydrogen production through electrolysis is not solely intended to meet end-user energy demand but can also be exported to industrial sectors as a feedstock or utilised as a fuel for transport applications, such as heavy-duty vehicles. While, the FC is primarily designed to cover local energy demands.

As HSS capacity increased, BESS capacity expanded subtly from 23.31 MWh to 23.91 MWh, showcasing that lower hydrogen costs do not replace BESS but instead promote a more complementary interaction between storage technologies. Conversely, the increased HSS led to a slight reduction in TES capacity, decreasing between 3.68 MWh and 2.93 MWh, which shows reduced reliance on TES. The growth of HSS also modestly decreased PV capacity, but it increased WT capacity, nearly doubling it. The results generally highlight that reductions in hydrogen CAPEX enhance the economic competitiveness of hydrogen-based technologies and reshape system design towards higher hydrogen penetration in decentralised energy systems.

4 Conclusion

This research develops a decentralised grid-independent tri-generation system that combines renewable energy, HP, and hybrid energy storage systems, including HSS, BESS, and TES. Linear programming is employed to optimise both the design and operation of the system.

The findings show that energy input is dominated by solar PV due to its year-round stability, whereas WT contributes only marginally under site-specific resource and economic conditions. System operation is strongly influenced by seasonal demand, with winter exhibiting the highest electricity and heating demand, while cooling demand is concentrated in summer.

The hybrid storage configuration improves the allocation of storage functions across short- and long-term timescales. BESS mainly provides short-term electrical balance, TES supports thermal flexibility, and HSS facilitates long-term energy support during energy shortages. The inclusion of HSS reduces the required BESS and TES capacities by approximately 11% and 6%, respectively. This hybrid structure manages the trade-off between cost and system operation to overcome energy shortfalls, resulting in a more balanced and economically favourable system design.

Despite a substantial 90% reduction in hydrogen CAPEX, the total annualised system cost decreases by only approximately 2.2%, indicating a moderate sensitivity of system economics to hydrogen cost. Nevertheless, lower hydrogen costs promote HSS capacity expansion. Both hydrogen storage and FC micro-CCHP capacities climb to four times of the baseline investment cost to 8.38 MWh and 0.44 MW, respectively. At the same time, the electrolyser capacity increases significantly to 0.79 MW. The findings showcase that cost reductions stimulate hydrogen production to cover multiple local energy demands and offer potential value for hydrogen trading within the system.

Integrating multi-energy storage offers a robust pathway to improve system performance and cost-effectiveness in decentralised hydrogen-based trigeneration systems, particularly under seasonal variability and resource intermittency.

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